

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Precarious migrants in domestic cleaning work. Findings from Finland

Sector report

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Executive Summary

This report discusses the experiences of migrant workers in Finland's domestic work sector, focusing on how precarious migration status affects working conditions and everyday life. The study, part of the I-CLAIM research project, draws on interviews with workers and stakeholders to explore the interplay between migration status, everyday life and employment.

Finnish labour legislation does not include a specific domestic work category; rather, domestic work encompasses various tasks, from household cleaning to assisting people with disabilities at home. The organisation of work in the sector is influenced by cultural values and welfare, gender and migration regimes. The demand for outsourced domestic work and cleaning services has grown in recent decades, despite Finland's extensive welfare state providing childcare and elderly care, and the share of migrant workers in the sector is increasing. Cleaning is the most common job for migrants, and 32% of all cleaners are foreigners. While most migrant workers hold regular residence status and formal employment contracts, informal employment persists in domestic cleaning, especially occasional cash-for-cleaning jobs, and among migrants with precarious legal status. As a labour shortage sector, cleaning and domestic work was long exempt from labour market testing in all regions of the country and continues to be in most regions. This means that it is possible for a non-EU worker to regularise their residence through employment in this sector. However, legislation introduced in autumn 2024 restricts asylum seekers with negative decisions from applying for work-based residence permits, thereby creating barriers to regularisation through work.

Migrant workers find employment in this sector through different channels. Often, they work through agencies, through direct employment with employer-households, or are hired by a municipality. A special arrangement is the so-called 'cleaning circle', whereby multiple households collectively hire a cleaner, thus providing a potential route for regularisation.

We interviewed 20 workers and 12 stakeholders. The participants included migrants from diverse backgrounds and were primarily women. The interviews revealed that precarious residence status leads to vulnerability and even exploitation, with informal side work being common. Migrant workers face multiple challenges, including dependency on employers and health risks. The entanglement of residence permits and labour markets creates vulnerabilities, with temporary permits affecting life plans and increasing susceptibility to abuse.

This study highlights the precariousness of migrant workers in Finland's domestic work sector—a precariousness exacerbated by restrictive migration policies. While for many domestic and cleaning work offers a potential route to a regular residence in Finland, broader policy changes are needed to protect workers, reduce their dependency on employers, and provide access to more stable residence permit types.

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1. Introduction

This report is based on ethnographic research, which focuses on the experiences of migrant workers in the domestic work sector in Finland. We examine how precarious, irregular, or temporary migration status impacts migrants' access to employment, their working conditions, and how migration status and work impact their everyday life and the lives of their families. By interviewing workers about their current and past experiences in this sector, as well as other relevant stakeholders, we examine the entanglements between working life, residence status, and everyday life.

The domestic work sector includes different jobs and ways of organising labour, from house cleaning to assisting people with disabilities in their daily lives. Welfare, gender, and migration regimes, as well as cultural notions and values related to care, shape the organisation of care and domestic work and the role of migrants in this sector (Kilkey et al., 2010; Näre, 2012). We explore the Finnish context of caring and cleaning work performed at home and discuss migrant workers' roles in this sector. We focus our analysis on house cleaning work, as it is the most typical kind of domestic work in our data. Moreover, cleaning work in general is not just work often done by workers with a migrant background; it is also strategically important work, as it has long been a way through which precarious migrants have been able to regularise their residence in Finland. We also present the case of so-called 'cleaning circles', in which a group of households come together to hire a full-time cleaner to provide the worker with a route to regularisation or family reunification.

2. Domestic Work in Finland

Finnish labour legislation does not recognise the category of domestic work, although the statistics entail data on professions such as domestic helpers (*kotiapulainen*), domestic cleaners (*kotisiivoja*), personal assistants (*henkilökohtainen avustaja*) and home care workers (*kotipalvelutyöntekijä*). While estimations of the number of domestic workers in Finland vary depending on who is included in the category, the sector has grown in recent years. If we consider home care workers, domestic cleaners and housekeepers there are around 22,000–25,000 workers in the sector (Statistics Finland, 2025). The share of migrants has increased, and currently over 11% of all domestic workers and 40% of domestic cleaners are migrants, mostly from the Philippines (Statistics Finland, 2025).

The above numbers include municipal care services provided to provided homes and exclude informally employed workers. In 2001, Finland implemented a tax credit for household work as a policy measure intended to prevent informal employment by subsidising the private employment of domestic workers (Näre, 2016). However, it is not clear whether the tax credit has influenced tax evasion (Kangas & Kalliomaa-Puha, 2024). Our empirical research indicates that for migrants whose legal status is precarious or who have lost their residence permits, informal cleaning is, similar to platform-based food delivery, an easy way to access some income (Maury et al., [Forthcoming]).

House cleaning and all kinds of domestic work were traditionally the domain of working-class women, but in recent decades, the sector has seen a sharp increase in migrant labour (Käyhkö, 2006; Saukkonen, 2022). Nowadays, cleaning is the most common job for migrants in Finland. As of 2022, 32% of all cleaners in Finland are foreigners, while their share of all workers is 9% (Statistics Finland, 2025). Domestic work and cleaning are in most regions of the country included in labour shortage sectors, and between 2015 and 2025, this was also true for the capital region of Helsinki. In a labour shortage sector, a non-EU migrant can be

hired without assessing the availability of national or EU workers for the job (i.e. labour market testing). This simplifies the process of hiring a non-EU citizen and applying for a residence permit based on employment. The work in the sector qualifies for a work-based residence permit if the employment is full-time and the contract follows collective agreements, or if monthly earnings exceed €1,600 after tax. Exemption from labour market testing incentivises migrants to find employment in this sector, regardless of their education, skills and qualifications, thus steering them into low-skilled and low-paid work (Wide, 2023).

While most foreign workers in Finland hold regular residence and work statuses, and informal work in general is relatively rare, some irregular side arrangements are typical to this sector. For example, a full-time contracted cleaner may occasionally clean a private household for cash. Some tasks may be performed outside agreed-upon working hours and remain undeclared and/or underpaid by the employer. It is difficult to estimate the prevalence of informality or its financial relevance to the sector, as these are often occasional rather than permanent arrangements.

In Finland, most residence statuses allow for work, although some have attendant restrictions. For example, asylum seekers have the full right to work either three or six months after arriving, depending on their travel documents. Ukrainian beneficiaries of the Temporary Protection Directive have an immediate unlimited right to work, while student visa holders may work a maximum of 30 hours per week. A person whose permit ends and for whom a renewal permit or asylum application is rejected loses their right to work. Work-based permits are, however, always issued for a given sector; thus, an agricultural worker taking up occasional cleaning is breaching regulations.

Migration legislation in Finland since September 2024 prohibits individuals who have sought asylum and have received a negative decision from applying for work-based residence permits (Merikoski et al., 2024). This leaves many in a dead end, with no right to work, only minimal social and welfare support, and no way to regularise, even if they manage to find employment. Those who have been irregularised for other reasons, such as job loss, may be regularised again with a new job if the employment fulfils the criteria for an employment-based residence permit. However, the new legislation also punishes for irregular stay in the country. Thus, one may be rejected if their old permit expires while seeking employment even if they meet the other requirements for the permit. Moreover, since June 2025, non-EU migrants who have been in the country less than two years have only three months to find new employment in the event that they become unemployed and cannot find work in a sector that is considered 'highly skilled'. Cleaning work used to be an 'easy' route to regularise, as it was long exempted from labour market testing in Helsinki metropolitan region where most migrants live. While it has not been exempted since June 2024, these assessments change every six months. Cleaning is a sector that is in constant need of a flexible labour force that is willing to work for low wages and where knowledge of the local language is not always needed.

Types of Domestic Work in Finland

The prevalence of paid domestic work has changed over the past century, with demand decreasing with the expansion of the welfare state that began in the 1960s. Although the Finnish welfare state continues to be relatively extensive and many caring tasks are provided by public services, the use of commercial domestic services is increasing. Paying for domestic services has become more common and less stigmatised (Näre, 2016). This increased demand is due in part to the increased working hours and career demands of professionals (Wide, 2024). While outsourcing occasional cleaning is relatively common among middle-class households, outsourcing childcare is rarer. Households that hire nannies are typically high-income

dual-earner households in which the parents want to ease their time-pressed everyday lives and maximise the quality of the time they spend with their children (Näre & Wide, 2019).

Cleaning is a very gendered work sector where 80% of workers are women. While Finnish men are rare in the sector (15%), migrant men cleaners comprise a 33% share (Statistics Finland, 2025). The share of migrant workers is highest in Helsinki metropolitan region where they comprised 63% of cleaners in 2022 (Saukkonen, 2022). Migrants who perform cleaning and domestic work typically have a background in non-EU countries, with the exception of Estonia and some Eastern European countries. The most prevalent countries of origin are the former Soviet Union countries (including Estonia), the Philippines, Thailand, Somalia, Nigeria, Nepal, Iraq and Bangladesh (Statistics Finland, 2024).

In our data, cleaning work is the most prominent type of domestic work, with more than half of our participants having worked as cleaners (N = 13). The others worked at care jobs (N = 7) with various arrangements and job titles. Typically, cleaning jobs are performed by the employees of a company from which households buy cleaning services by the hour. Many migrants who work in cleaning work in both public and private spaces.

The so-called cleaning circle is a special arrangement invented for the purpose of regularising a migrant with precarious status. The worker may be a person already in the country and at risk of being irregularised, or the circle can be used to organise migration to Finland from unsafe countries where few migration options exist, such as Afghanistan (see Section 5.3).

Some participants had worked primarily in care-related tasks, including childcare and elderly care. These are all jobs for which the employer might be a municipality, an agency or a private person. The Finnish welfare state provides care for these groups in publicly funded care institutions, by outsourcing it to private service providers or by supporting the purchase of these services with tax benefits and/or subsidies given to households. Hired full-time nannies, however, are not widely employed, as all children in Finland under school age have the right to a place in kindergarten which are relatively inexpensive or, in the case of low-income families, free. Nevertheless, our research participants included three full-time nannies and domestic workers and one live-in domestic worker. All three were from the Philippines and worked for wealthy, professional families. In addition, we interviewed two people with elderly care experience. In Finland, most ageing individuals continue to live at home with the support of homecare provided during carefully timed home visits (Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare, 2025). Other ageing individuals live in assisted living units or care homes. Some participants had worked as carers or cleaners in live-in elder care institutions. Hiring a personal live-in caregiver at home outside of municipal service provision is rare. Two of our research participants had worked as a personal assistant to a person with disability.

3. Methods and Data

We interviewed both workers (N = 20) and experts and stakeholders (N = 12), either in person in the capital region or via video call, depending on the location of the participant. With the help of our research assistants, we conducted some interviews in Ukrainian, Vietnamese, Arabic and English, while a few were conducted in Dari or Somali with the help of a stakeholder in translating, and a few required a mix of languages. As research assistants, we employed students from who shared a language with the participants, and who had cultural knowledge or shared experiences with them. The assistants' input was crucial for us during the field

work, and they influenced the research process by suggesting approaches and questions for the interviews and by actively participating in the conversations.

The interviews were semi-structured, covering themes related to migration history, legal status, working and living conditions, and the household dimension. Most interviews covered all key questions in the first meeting. The average length of each interview was one and a half to two hours.

We conducted follow-up interviews with a selection of participants (N = 6), holding free discussions around the themes of migration, intimate life/family, work and future dreams by using photographs or objects of their choosing as inspiration. The purpose of objects in an object-oriented interview is not only to inspire storytelling or represent some events or experiences in the participants' past, but also to enable those experiences to materialise in the moment and over time (Harrison et al., 2024).

Our research participants were Ukrainian, Vietnamese, Afghan, Filipino, Iraqi, Somali, Moroccan and Tunisian. A majority (N = 17) were women aged from 20–47 years. Their initial reasons for arriving in Finland varied, but most did not migrate primarily for domestic work. Many had experience in both sectors we studied for I-CLAIM: agriculture and domestic work. Some were forced migrants, and several had migrated for family reasons. All the names mentioned in this report are pseudonyms. The research participants' time could not be compensated with vouchers due to Finnish tax regulations, but we offered refreshments during the interviews and bought food for undocumented research participants. We also assisted the research participants with information on migration policies or social services.

4. Cleaning for Papers and Money: Main Ethnographic Findings

Cleaning work has been a way for many migrants in irregular or precarious situations to regularise their residence. Before the recent changes in Finnish migration policies that block rejected asylum seekers from applying for employment-based residence permits, finding a job in a labour shortage sector was one of the best ways out of irregularity for irregularised migrants (Merikoski et al., 2024). Cleaning and domestic work has also been a route to enter the country, as for many years cleaners could be hired directly from abroad without labour market testing. According to the interviewed stakeholders, cleaning work is also one of the most typical sectors in which undocumented migrants are employed (also Jokinen & Ollus, 2014). As domestic cleaning is done away from public view and occasional cash jobs are available, it is one of the easiest ways to earn money for someone with no residence or working rights, despite the risk of being exploited in informal work.

4.1. Irregularity and Precarity in Domestic Work and the Cleaning Sector

In Finland, many cleaners and domestic workers hold residence permits through their employment, albeit conditional and temporary (Wide, 2024). Domestic work can also be performed by individuals with other migration statuses, such as asylum seekers who have unlimited right to work during the time their claim is processed. Informality and irregularity are most often related to aspects other than residence status, such as doing extra hours off the books. However, many participants had at some point found themselves temporarily in between statuses or at risk of falling into an irregular situation if a permit was about to expire and its renewal was uncertain.

Employment-based residence statuses create precarity due to the temporariness of residence permits. As these permits need to be renewed regularly, they create dependency on the continuation of the employment contract. Because of this dependency, the worker has a high threshold for complaining to authorities if they are treated poorly or paid unfairly, as their residence permit is tied to employment (Pekkarinen & Jokinen, 2023). Employers hold significant power over workers' status and, concomitantly, over many aspects of their and their families' lives (Merikoski et al., 2024).

Migrants working in the cleaning sector are vulnerable to exploitation at work (Ollus, 2016). Those who are recruited directly from abroad, either by recruitment agencies or private employers, easily become dependent on both recruiters and employers. While completely irregular work and residency are relatively rare in Finland, quite often there are informal arrangements on the side of formal employment, and exploitative informal arrangements sometimes occur. For example, while the work may be regular on paper—in which the worker has a contract and necessary employer payments such as pension, sickness insurance and paid vacation days—in practice the worker works more hours or for less wages than what is specified in the contract.

Informal Gigs and Occasional Cleaning-for-Cash

The need for occasional for-cash work may arise from not having the formal right to work due to one's residence permit situation. For instance, Linh did not have the right to work, as she was still engaged in applying for a labour-based residence permit. To survive, she did occasional cleaning work under her friend's name and account, and her friend paid her in cash.

Sometimes, the need for informal gigs arises from the risk of losing one's welfare benefits. Many cleaners earn so little that they are entitled to housing benefits to supplement their monthly incomes. However, the housing benefit is cut if one earns more money. Valentina lives in Finland with a temporary protection permit. She has two children, both of whom live in Finland: the younger child lives with her, and the older child lives on their own. Valentina has a low-paying but formal office-cleaning job in a cleaning company, but she also takes on occasional house-cleaning gigs for cash from people she knows through friends. This extra money enables her to support her adult child, who is struggling financially:

“Yes, I worked illegally. Cleaning, washing windows and all that. Yes, thank you for giving me this job, because it's hard it's good that you can still make money this way. It was a one-off job, just like that.... It's not much, though, €50 a week. But at least it's some help, I can ... send it to my child to buy food.” (Valentina, Ukrainian)

She explained that it can be difficult to find informal work because, in her words, “Finnish people ‘are afraid of undocumented workers”.

Sometimes, irregular arrangements are initiated by the employer. For example, working hours may turn out to be different from what was specified in the contract, or the worker may be asked to perform different tasks than what was initially agreed upon. Au pairing is a curious case that is often considered a form of cultural exchange. Although legislation views it as a kind of non-work, it may nevertheless resemble an employment relationship in practice and sometimes an exploitative one (e.g. Cox & Busch, 2018; Wide, 2025). Maria, who also had agricultural work experience in Finland, worked for a period as a nanny through the au-pair system. Despite being officially an au pair, she worked several days a week in the host family's café and did other

tasks for the hosts, such as house cleaning. In the case of Hien, a Vietnamese student, her landlady encouraged her to take on informal work to earn money on the side of her studies, so she ended up cleaning the house of her landlady's relative without a contract.

4.2. Precarity of Status, Working Conditions and Everyday Life for the Workers

While only some participants had lived in Finland with an irregularised status, residence in the country was temporary and conditional for all. Temporariness of status dominated their everyday lives and future plans in many ways, as being able to continue living in Finland and build their lives and homes there was tainted with uncertainty. The ever-present possibility of falling from a regular status to an irregular one conditions the choices of migrant workers. Thus, the entanglement of the residence permit regime and labour markets was crucial in determining our participants' experiences of living and working in Finland.

Their vulnerability to abusive situations at work was enhanced by the migration regime, with different residence statuses creating different kinds of vulnerabilities. Work-based residence permits are given to a certain sector and tied to the employer, and while changing employers within a sector is possible with some additional paperwork, the dependency makes workers vulnerable. When applying for a permit, the employer must provide documentation for the application. Sometimes, the employer withholds the documents to pressure the worker to do extra work without pay. The threshold for complaining or demanding better working conditions is high when both livelihood and residence status are tied to one's job.

Migrants who have a status through family reunification or international protection are not dependent on a job, but their residence in the country is still temporary and precarious. The current migration regime increases this temporality and has made the requirements for permanent residence or citizenship stricter, and it matters whether a person holds an A- or B-type residence permit. For example, many of the Ukrainian participants who held Temporary Protection permits (B-type) were worried about their future in Finland. Not knowing about the future of Temporary Protection Directive was stressful. Living with a B-type residence permit counts as half the time actually spent in the country. For this reason, many Ukrainian participants sought any employment that would qualify them for a work-based residence permit. The temporariness of almost all migration statuses renders migrant workers vulnerable and forces them into low-paid sectors with few options for upward mobility. Temporariness delays one's plans to learn the local language, which in turn delays one's chances of doing types of work other than migrantised, low-paid work. As Oksana put it:

"I don't plan anything right now. I dream of getting a permanent contract and going from temporary protection to a working visa. I want to learn Finnish, but I haven't had a chance yet... I want to learn the language, and I need to learn it." (Oksana, Ukrainian)

While cleaning work is often done by a person who is already in the country, some are directly employed from abroad. These cases often involve an agency or other kind of migration broker. Directly recruited domestic workers are vulnerable to exploitative working conditions, dependence on the employer, and conditions of servitude caused by the conditions of the labour-based permit combined with recruitment practices.

Undocumented Migrants and No Right to Work

Of the participants who had experience of being without a residence permit or without the right to work, none had been permanently employed in this sector during the time they were irregular. Some participants had been laid off when they lost their status and with it the right to work. Basem from Iraq had already worked as a home caregiver during his nursing studies, which he was able to start during his years in the asylum system. He had a job waiting for him after graduation in a care home, but after losing status, his job offer was withdrawn. This experience was quite typical of those who had been irregularised in Finland. Losing both residence status and the possibility of working legally rendered the participants extremely vulnerable to poverty.

Others had been promised good job opportunities in Finland by migration brokers prior to departure, and the length of time to obtain a work permit came as a surprise. Some arrived to learn that they had no job prospects after all. This was not an issue specific to this sector; we also heard of these cases in relation to forestry, agriculture and other types of work. With the relative absence of non-exploitative informal work to be found and with a fear of the consequences of working informally, many of the irregular migrants we interviewed had very little working experience in Finland. This resonates with what we heard in stakeholder interviews: that it is extremely difficult to live and work in Finland without a status, and many migrants who have few chances of regularising their status move to other European countries, where it is easier to live irregularly and find informal work. Jasmin had moved from the Philippines to Finland to study for her practical nursing degree. The consultancy that had recruited the students had promised that it would be easy to find part-time jobs in Finland and that no Finnish language would be needed. This was not the case, and after one semester, Jasmin was only able to find an informal cleaning job that was insufficient to pay her student fees and living expenses. She decided to discontinue her studies and moved to Spain to work as an irregular live-in domestic worker, expecting to obtain a residence permit in the next amnesty for irregularised migrants.

4.3. Cleaning Circles: Domestic Labour Recruitment as a Solidarity Response

Of the different kinds of house cleaning work studied in this research, so-called cleaning circles stand out from the others. In the aftermath of the asylum ‘crisis’ of 2015, local pro-asylum activists began forming these circles to regularise rejected asylum seekers. These individuals, often from Iraq or Afghanistan, had no other way of regularising their residence in Finland, and many were at risk of being stuck in a limbo of negative decisions and appeal applications or of being deported to an unsafe country. Cleaning circle activity was developed by activists closely connected to other forms of pro-asylum solidarity mobilisation in Finland that emerged in 2015–2017 as a result of the ‘crisis’ and its resulting migration policy restrictions, such as home accommodation for asylum seekers (Merikoski, 2020) and the asylum seekers’ Right to Live demonstration (Näre, 2020). At the time, cleaning was a labour shortage sector and thus one of the only sectors of work into which a non-EU migrant could be hired without labour market testing, including in the capital region. In a cleaning circle, up to 25 households commit to paying a predetermined sum of money for a bi-monthly cleaning (sometimes weekly or monthly) contract. The money collected is used to offer a full-time employment contract and salary to the employee and also to pay the employers’ costs, such as pension, insurance and holiday pay. As an employed person, the worker can then apply for a work-based residence permit.

We encountered three situations that were typical of the ways in which these circles were set up. First are circles designed for a migrant already in the country to be able to regularise their residence. Second, circles are set up to help those migrants who are still in their country and are struggling to get out. This was more typical in the case of Afghanistan, especially since the Taliban coup in 2021, which made life unbearable for

many. These individuals were often relatives of someone who had migrated earlier to Finland and who were able to mobilise support for the operation. While many who arrived like this originate in conditions that would qualify them for international protection, and they often did apply for asylum once they reached Finland, it is a safer route to take than what asylum seekers typically endure. As one of the interviewed coordinators, Minna, said:

“Compared to other asylum seekers, they have been able to arrive in a relatively humane way. No smugglers, no long journeys. There’s no eight-year asylum process or living in a reception centre. So, I think this is a very humane way, and it saves people from a lot of trauma and burden. Of course, they already have, based on what’s going on there in the home country, fear for their loved ones, and so on, but no added trauma from the journey. Then, they are welcomed by tens of families who have been waiting for them. So, it is a softer kind of migration experience. And even then, it is difficult.” (Minna, cleaning circle coordinator)

Family reunification is the third typical situation for which the circle is a solution. After the worker has received their own residence permit, through circle work or otherwise, they need to earn enough money monthly to sponsor their families to Finland. Currently, a sponsor needs a monthly net income of €2,300 to sponsor a spouse and two children, €2,660 for a spouse and three children, and increasing with each child (Migri, 2025a). The median Finnish salary is about €3,300 gross, or approximately €2,500 after taxes – if the same rule were applied to all Finns, almost half would not be allowed three children. It is also more than most workers in cleaning make, especially if it is not a full-time job.

In cleaning circles with more than 20 households, the cleaners have full-time jobs, and their income is stable as long as none of the households drop out. This does not mean that there is no exploitation or dependency on the organisers of the cleaning circles. Aryana’s husband’s brother arranged for Aryana to move from Afghanistan to Finland with the help of his Finnish wife, who arranged a cleaning circle to employ Aryana. She took debts from various family members to pay for the travel and left her husband and children in Afghanistan with the idea that she would arrange for family reunification in Finland. She moved in with her husband’s brother and his wife, but once in Finland, they demanded that she pay €600 rent for a room in their flat. This, in addition to the costs of sending money back home, was too expensive, so she decided to move into a reception centre after applying for asylum (Aryana, Afghanistan).

Many research participants had little direct interaction with service receivers. For example, some had never met the people whose homes they cleaned. The cleaning circle stands out for its greater involvement in the private lives and families of workers. Organisers of cleaning circles and some individual employer households were often actively involved, not just in the process of permit application for the worker and their family members but also in other issues regarding their settlement in Finland. Elisa explained that their circle’s worker’s family finally arrived through family reunification, so she and others from the circle helped them find a home to rent and provided them with information about social security and school systems in Finland. Material forms of assistance were also typical, such as collecting money for the worker’s family’s travel costs or gathering used clothes and furniture to help the family settle. Some employers even suggested using part of the paid cleaning time to teach Finnish to workers so that they could help with both integration and employment.

Although the initial motivation for many households to become employers in a cleaning circle is to support a precarious migrant settling in Finland, attitudes sometimes shifted over time. All the interviewed cleaning

circle coordinators told us that some employer households complained about the quality of cleaning or about their need to pay even when a worker was ill and could not work, despite the fact that, as employers, the law required them to do. While there was a shared understanding among most employer households that the cleaner is not a professional cleaner and that they might need guidance and time to adjust to the tasks, some households felt that they did not get their money's worth. Thus, as regular households would occasionally drop out and replacements had to be found, most coordinators had their hands full.

4.4. The Health and Wellbeing of Precarious Migrant Workers

As many of the jobs under the umbrella of domestic work are physical, significant health risks are involved. The work hazards that include toxic chemicals, heavy lifting, physical and verbal assault from employers, patients or their family members, a lack of rest and food for live-in workers, and psychological and physiological effects from long work hours and night work (Kurowski et al., 2015). Many participants mentioned the inadequate time allocated for the completion of their work and haste increases the risk of injury. Cleaning companies typically allocate minimum times for jobs (which must be reported in an electronic system), and travel time is often unpaid. Time for eating and resting is minimal. The cleaning circle stands out because the work schedule is often planned to minimise demands on the worker. Workers usually clean two households a day, and the travel time between locations is counted as working time.

The participants' experiences regarding access to public or private health care varied greatly as access to health care services depends on one's residence status and employment. By law, irregularised migrants have the right to use municipal health services when seeking immediate and necessary care. However, the current government intends to restrict access to immediate care only. Ukrainians with Temporary Protection status may become residents of a municipality and thus be included in municipal services. However, having access does not necessarily mean experiencing good service; much depends on the municipality and how medical staff encounter their patients. Some had the experience of not being listened to, particularly when the matter concerned a non-immediate, still tolerable, but worsening issue. In contrast, some participants had very positive experiences when dealing with the health care system, including some who had been without a status for some time.

Those with an asylum-seeker background had the worst experiences. Asylum seekers' health services are managed through reception and not through the regular municipal health and social service system. For example, Maryam lost her family-based status after divorce and, in the absence of other regularisation routes, was forced to apply for asylum. She subsequently lost access to her social worker and municipal health centre and was stuck in limbo for seven years before being regularised. Her issues were downplayed when she sought help in the reception centre for severe aches and illnesses. She then had to wait a month for a doctor's appointment to get medication. Especially hurtful were the words of a nurse who told her to go to the gym and lose weight. Her multiple pains were worsened by occasional cleaning jobs. In addition, financial uncertainty combined with worries about the future and the asylum decision all took their toll on her mental and physical health, but the support she received was inadequate.

Linh, from Vietnam, who was mentioned earlier, found herself in a difficult situation: her short-term permit had ended, and her new application based on studies was refused. She could not go back due to no longer having a job to return to, as well as the large debts she had taken on to migrate. Moreover, shortly after arriving in Finland, she found that she was pregnant. Although she was entitled to health care, she did not dare to access it because she was afraid that the immigration service would hear of it and deny her

application. She spoke no Finnish or English, which made seeking help even more difficult. She had received vouchers (which can be used for food, sanitary products, diapers, etc.) from social services but did not dare to use those either. Towards the end of her pregnancy, a source whom she trusted told her that she could safely see a doctor. Ultimately, she was able to have her pregnancy and birth properly monitored at the hospital. She also eventually used the vouchers. However, she had missed early scans and check-ups, and even later on, she and her baby relied mainly on the help of friends from her own community.

Sarita, a live-in domestic worker we interviewed, experienced problems that are common in these work arrangements, including lack of sufficient rest during workdays, dependency on the employer and problems getting enough to eat during the day (see, e.g., Näre, 2012). Despite being told that she could take anything from the fridge, she was reprimanded for doing so and told that she had eaten food intended for the employer's family dinner. She did not have her own kitchen, so her diet consisted mainly of canned foods. These examples highlight the various aspects of vulnerability caused by precarious residence status and by working and living in someone else's home.

4.5. Gendered Implications of Precarious Residence and Cleaning Work

Gendered vulnerability is worsened by precarious residence status and family-based permits that put pressure on partners to maintain relationships. For example, Zena was in an abusive relationship, and her husband thought she would never dare to leave him, because her permit was tied to their marriage. Nevertheless, she left and two and a half years later is still trying to regularise her residence for other reasons, as her short-term victim's permit has ended.

Migration can lead to increased independence, even when one's residence status is temporary. Many Ukrainian women were raising children on their own, which meant a lot of time-related emotional and financial strain. Many had been able to gain independence from their husbands through the earnings they made working in Finland. Also, Naima, an Afghan woman, was able to lead a much freer life, as she was able to escape not just the Taliban but patriarchal society and some conservative family members through her work in a cleaning circle.

We interviewed several men who worked in cleaning, and their experiences varied based on their status and the jobs they were doing. Men who had worked in cleaning sometimes reflected on being a man doing cleaning work, which indicates that it was something they had had to consider. In cleaning circle interviews, the male gender was often discussed, both with workers and with circle organisers or employers. Many workers in cleaning circles are Afghan or Iraqi men, and often they had never previously had to clean. While most took it as a challenge and were willing to learn and even laugh about it, some employers felt that perhaps their workers' pride had been wounded by having to resort to cleaning work. For example, one man had not wanted to change sheets as part of his tasks, as he apparently felt this was too intimate and he had never before done anyone else's laundry. In contrast, educated and middle-class women who worked in house cleaning were usually familiar with such tasks.

4.6. Racial and Ethnic Segregation in the Sector

Racialisation is present most clearly at the structural level in the migranticisation of certain types of work and in differentiated control of residence permits for different nationalities. Moreover, the systematic pushing of non-EU migrants to low-paid and low-skilled sectors of work and to the lowest levels of hierarchies within these sectors can already be perceived as a form of structural othering and racialisation.

Bureaucratic bordering (Näre & Maury, 2024) affects some groups more than others. For example, the requirements for certain types of identification documents disadvantage some groups of migrant workers: Somali citizens' passports are not accepted for employment-based residence permit applications because these identification documents are categorically not considered credible (Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2025). Another group with great difficulties consists of Afghans belonging to the Hazara minority, who are required to hold the identity documents *tazkiras* when applying, although getting a *tazkira* poses multiple issues for them. Moreover, as Afghanistan does not have an embassy in Finland, Afghans who want to apply for passports need to take the risk of travelling to Stockholm without documents.

Societally and culturally, there are racial stereotypes about wanted workers and naturalised aptitudes for certain kinds of work. Often, these forms of structural, institutional and cultural racialisation overlap. For example, women from the Philippines are considered desirable workers for all kinds of caring tasks, but their work and wages are often deskilled so that they must work in jobs lower than their qualifications (a registered nurse may be hired as a care assistant). Moreover, they often face difficulties when trying to bring their families to Finland due to restrictive family reunification policies, which make it difficult for people at their income level to sponsor a family.

5. Concluding Remarks

Administrative struggles regarding residence permits are entangled with migrant workers' precarious living and working conditions. Employers hold significant power over a person's status and, concomitantly, over many aspects of their and their family's lives (Merikoski et al., 2024). While dependency is not limited to cleaning work—indeed, it applies to all labour-based residence permits—it is particularly significant in this sector because cleaning is the most common job for migrants in Finland, regardless of their qualifications or gender. The gendered and racialised composition of the cleaning sector is visible when we consider that while Finnish men do engage in cleaning, especially domestic cleaning, only rarely, it not at all an uncommon job for migrant men from non-EU countries.

Cleaning work can be relatively easy to access for individuals who have no legal status or right to work. As domestic cleaning in particular takes place within the privacy of households, it offers earning opportunities for irregular migrants without having to worry about labour inspections or other controls. However, workers in such situations are at the mercy of their employer, and the earnings are meagre.

While until 2024 it used to be possible to regularise one's residence and apply for a labour-based permit through domestic cleaning as long as the contract followed collective agreements, the current government has made it impossible for previous asylum seekers to apply for labour-based permits once they are in Finland (Migri, 2025b). Furthermore, according to the revised assessment of labour shortage jobs in the Helsinki metropolitan region, domestic cleaning is no longer free from labour market testing; thus, recruiting workers for domestic work directly from abroad is no longer a viable option.

While salaries in domestic cleaning are so low that it is very difficult to earn enough with one job to comply with the high-income limits for family reunification, solidarity-based cleaning circles offer relatively higher earnings and hence better opportunities for family reunification. However, this does mean that mistreatment and relationships of dependency are completely absent from cleaning circles. Thus, there is a need to develop policies that better protect workers and sanction employers and contractors in cases of labour exploitation.

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